

THE CURRENT STATE OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE CULTURE IN CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This In the article, the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan It is analytically explained that the introduction of a new social system is based on family traditions, and that the relations between corporate culture groups and small activity groups between state and private cultural organizations are based on this culture . Also in the article, the current state of the corporate culture system in our country you will get acquainted with the suggestions and recommendations of the author on the effective use of the given opportunities.*

Key words: *culture, formation, corporate culture, development, effective, conditions, New Uzbekistan.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda madaniyat muassasalarida korporativ madaniyatning shakllanishi va rivojlanishining hozirgi holati oilaviy an‘analarga asoslangan yangi ijtimoiy tizimning joriy etilishiga asoslanib, korporativ madaniyat guruhleri bilan davlat va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi munosabatlar tahliliy ravishda bayon etilgan. xususiy madaniyat tashkilotlari bu madaniyatga asoslanadi. Shuningdek, maqolada muallifning mamlakatimizdagi korporativ madaniyat tizimining bugungi holati berayotgan imkoniyatlardan samarali foydalanishga oid taklif va tavsiyalari bilan tanishasiz.*

Калит сўзлар: *маданият, шаклланиши, корпоратив маданият, ривожлантириш, самарали, шарт-шароит, Янги Ўзбекистон.*

Аннотация: В данной статье современное состояние формирования и развития корпоративной культуры в учреждениях культуры Узбекистана основано на внедрении новой социальной системы, основанной на семейных традициях, и аналитически констатируется, что отношения между группами корпоративной культуры и общественностью и частные культурные организации основаны на этой культуре. Также в статье вы познакомитесь с предложениями и рекомендациями автора по эффективному использованию возможностей, предоставляемых современным состоянием системы корпоративной культуры в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: культура, формирование, корпоративная культура, развитие, эффективность, условия, Новый Узбекистан.

As we dwell on the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in the cultural institutions of our country, ensuring their competitiveness depends on the effectiveness of applying the theory and practice of corporate management. Therefore, the mechanism of corporate management, which is one of the modern and effective methods of managing the cultural sector, is the basis for the development of the cultural environment of our country.

Corporate governance is a set of laws and regulations that govern and regulate the activities of these institutions. It includes internal and external factors affecting the interests of customers, suppliers, and management bodies. Thus, the cultural institution controls itself, establishing its own values, policies and laws for employees from the highest to the lowest levels.

This system is undoubtedly the result of strong competition, and if it develops rapidly in the cultural institutions of Uzbekistan, we can take it to the leading positions in this field in the world. If we talk about the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in

Uzbekistan, first of all, it is necessary to train people in this direction, give referrals and give instructions on corporate culture. Otherwise they will not use this system. In our opinion, we do not believe that cultural institutions use this system as it is. After the Second World War, Russian thinking entered. The point of view of the former USSR can be considered completely outdated ¹. Even today, most of the managers support the same idea. However Cultural institutions in Uzbekistan feel uncomfortable in such a situation. In order to develop corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan when some powerful leader wants to lead people to his direction (manipulation), people behave as if they are following him. Basically, this method is very ineffective.

Development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan can include:

- to changes readiness
- important quality and is a customer
- innovations and marketing
- internationality
- accuracy and to payment ability

Corporate culture is very sensitive to change, quality, customer, innovation, marketing, internationality and clarity, accountability are of primary importance. When we change our clothes, we replace our old suit with a new one, but what is underneath the suit remains in place ². Similarly, the formation of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan remains unchanged and alive.

The best cultural institutions have been free of many disappointments for a long time, always trying to move the world together.

¹ Uzbekistan " Shareholding " of the Republic societies and of shareholders rights protection No. 370 dated 06.05.2014 law _

² Suyunov D.Kh. Corporate bosharuw mechanisms : muammo wa echimlar . Monograph. - T .: Academy, 2006.

Innovations and marketing have now entered the daily activities of cultural institutions in Uzbekistan . It is impossible for cultural institutions to survive in the competitive environment without holding these events.

In our view, the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan is facing problems related to differences in cultures, they are learning new culture and finding ways to meet the requirements of their customers. In order for this positive situation to survive in the future , it is important to maintain the behavioral factor, which can only be guaranteed through clarity and accountability.

The concept of changes can be used in a broad sense, that is:

- " Changes " global in the world main understanding ;
- In the system of cultural institutions changes ;
- management change ;
- also corporate culture promotion changes ;
- Logistics change _
- Organizational change and so _

Corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan is very important to ensure that many stakeholders, such as investors, shareholders, employees, customers, partners and society, are satisfied with their needs and interests. The most important feature of corporate management in cultural institutions is a precise planning strategy. In cultural institutions, it is important to strengthen the promotion and communication for their services. In addition, cultural institutions must establish their target audience and the problems they want to solve. Cultural institutions should define a strategic plan that allows them to reach the goals of the target audience through their services ³.

Based on the formation and improvement of the corporate governance system in cultural institutions, successful corporate governance operations require

³ Suyunov D.Kh. Corporate management . -T: Academy, 2013.

well-executed, effective policies, procedures and processes. This helps to reduce working time, increase productivity and achieve strategic goals. Discipline should be part of the organizational culture, so that employees at all levels feel obligated to follow the established procedure for each work process.

cultural institutions is to establish a fair relationship with all interested parties. Transparency is key to building trust within and outside the organization. Corporate governance features also include self-evaluation and continuous improvement. An important characteristic of corporate governance is corporate social responsibility. It should keep in mind the influence of cultural institutions on society. Cultural institutions should ensure that their activities work within the corporate culture system. Corporate culture Cultural institutions that focus on responsibility provide free services to specific groups of people and use sustainable development practices.

According to the research conducted on this topic and the analysis of available literature, a number of Uzbek scientists Berkinov B.B., Khodiev B.Yu., Khrshimov A.A., Suyunov D.Kh., Khamidullin M.B., Zaynutdinov Sh.N. Rakhimova D.N., Nurimbetov R.I. and others, it can be recognized that the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan has been researched. Also, Kh.N. Ruzmetova, T.P.Jiemuratov and A.N.Aripova conducted scientific studies on ⁴the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions of our country .

In the process of research, it is considered important to introduce and implement ways of increasing the effectiveness of the current state of formation and development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan in the era of digitization, which is the demand of the time. It is impossible to imagine the ⁵development of a strategy for expanding the cultural potential of the society to

⁴ Hamidulin M.B. Financial mechanisms of corporate governance. Monograph. - T.: Molya , 2008 .

⁵ Ashurov Z.A. " Corporate of management organizational and economic mechanism " / Monograph . T.: "LESSON PRESS" publishing house , 2019

increase the effectiveness of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan , modern corporate culture without intensive and consistent application of the latest information technologies .

General in a sense Corporate in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan culture manage issues :

- culture of institutions common meeting seeing exit procedure ;
- " modern place " problem removal verb for the choice and means done increase _
- performance activity of the executive body control come borders identification , information disclosed to do approaches and big corporate activity manage information transparency provide _

In conclusion, the formation of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan goes back to the distant past, but its development is very slow, and we cannot say that the current situation is satisfactory. Modern corporate legislation in cultural institutions of Uzbekistan increasingly reflects the best international standards, organizes information disclosure and management. It is possible to bring the corporate management system to a higher level by analyzing the scientific rules by which the modern model of regulating relations within cultural institutions in Uzbekistan is implemented. Establishing corporate culture and management relations in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan in its own way will undoubtedly serve the development of the industry.

REFERENCES USED

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protection of Joint-Stock Companies and Shareholders' Rights No. 370 dated 06.05.2014".
2. Suyunov D.Kh. Corporate management mechanism : problem and solutions . Monograph. - T.: Academy, 2006.
3. Suyunov D.Kh. Corporate management _ -T: Academy, 2013.

4. Hamidulin MB. Financial mechanisms of corporate governance. Monograph. - T.: Molya , 2008 .
5. Ashurov Z.A. " Corporate of management organizational and economic mechanism " / Monograph . T.: "LESSON PRESS" publishing house , 2019
6. Berkinov B.B. Corporate structures: fundamentals of creation and management. T.: INB im. Alishera Navoi ., 2005
7. Aripov A.N., Information and communications in the field management system improvement problems , i.f.n. _ get for dissertation , 2004 .
8. Adiljanovna, AM, Nurullaevna, NM, Abdumalikovna, YD, Sharobidinovich, MJ, Abdujalil Abduvalio'g'li, A., & Behzod Asqaralio'g'li, T. (2021). Academic Yunus Rajabi and His Scientific Heritage. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology* , 9092–9100.
- 9 . Abdumalikovna , YD (2021). The Role and Importance of Culture and Art in the Development of Society. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* , 3 , 1-3.
10. Juraevna, A. S., Abdumalikovna, Y. D., & Xusanovna, D. N. (2021). MODERN SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FUNCTIONS OF MUSIC ART AND EDUCATION. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(1), 57-59.
11. Teshabayeva , O. N., & Yuldasheva, D. A. (2022) . He is alone bank services the market management and development characteristics . *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal* , 1 (3), 91-97.
12. Sobirov, B., Yuldasheva, D., Iroda, N., & Laylo, T. (2022, February). MUSICAL WORKS AND THEIR PLACE IN HUMAN LIFE. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 53-56).
13. Achildiyeva, M., Khojimamatov, A., Dilafuz, Y., & Ikromova, F. (2021). Uyghur Folk Singing Genre. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(10).

14. Abdumalikovna, Y. D., & Adiljonovna, A. M. (2022). THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART EDUCATION IN OUR COUNTRY. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(8).

15. Yuldasheva, D. (2022). CREATIVE APPROACH TO CULTURE AND ART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Oriental renaissance : innovative , educational , natural oath social sciences* , 2 (10-2), 293-297.